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Teachers Perspective on Computer Technology and ICT Integration in Classroom Teaching

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Abstract

ICT integration in classroom teaching is one of the challenges that teachers face nowadays. Thus, this study aimed to determine the teachers' professional perspectives on computer technology and their process of integration in classroom teaching. The method used in this study was the descriptive-correlational research design to obtain the data needed specifically using survey questionnaire. Random sampling was used in selecting teachers per school as participants in the study for kindergarten to grade 6 Teachers in West 2 District, Division of Iligan City. Technology Implementation Questionnaire (TIQ) Version II tool was used. It was an adopted and modified instrument and developed by Wozney et al. (2006). Findings revealed that there is no significant difference in the factors affecting the respondent's professional perspective on the use of computer technology in the classroom. The results from regression analysis for the significant relationship between the respondents' professional view and their ICT process integration in terms of instructional, informative, communicative, evaluative, and organizational shows that there is a positive relationship among the variables mentioned except the informative ICT process integration. This implies that the professional perspective of the teachers has a positive influence on their ICT process integration in the classroom. Results showed that all the mentioned demographic profiles are not predictors of their ICT process integration as indicated in their p-values greater than 0.05 level of significance. The findings suggests that teachers should change their perspective about ICT integration, from traditional way of learning to more interactive learning.

Keywords: *classroom teaching, ICT integration, ICT competence, teachers perspective, computer technology*

Introduction

Education today is rapidly changing and evolving, especially the integration of ICT into classroom teaching has become the prime focus for educators and researchers. ICT is relevant as it aids a wide range of digital tools, online resources, storage, and information. From traditional blackboards to educational software, from group activities; to online collaborative platforms to mobile applications. ICT gives a multitude of opportunities to enhance teaching and learning experiences. The rapid growth of ICT has transformed learners into digital learners, requiring teachers to integrate and be more knowledgeable with the updated digital tools to integrate technology into their pedagogical approaches.

Teachers' attitudes, technological knowledge, and skills play a significant role in its effective integration (Akram et al, 2022). ICT integration in classroom teaching is one of the issues in today's education. The 21st century education has standards for teachers and one qualification is the mastery to use and integrate ICT into classroom instruction. Educators should have sufficient knowledge about computer technology and ICT integration in classroom teaching to enhance traditional teaching or increase productivity in the teaching and learning process (Porter & Graham, 2022).

Teachers' perspective towards ICT integration in classroom teaching should be positive, as it influences their development of ICT skills and their level of integration of ICT in educational activities. It can be used to reduce workload and share information with other teachers and with the learners. Teachers should change their perspective on ICT and be open-minded to change. Moreover, Al Bataineh (2022) claimed that the importance of technology must also be taken into account while discussing instruction or education concerns. Technology is important for teachers, especially in creating various activities for their lessons. They were viewed as major players engaging technology in the teaching and learning process to create a creative learning environment. However, ICT integration in classroom instruction has its disputes, particularly when it comes to execution and exploiting teachers' knowledge as first-time users of ICT. Other concerns include lack of use of digital tools, lack of ICT training, effectiveness, and technical support concerns for teachers using ICT. Therefore, these issues must be acknowledged to keep up with the current technological period, and teachers should be given the responsibility of incorporating ICT into their instruction.

Being an essential part of the present time, Information and communication technology (ICT) significantly influences all domains of human life (Gnamb, 2021). Similarly, ICT has also transformed the education sector and turned instructional practices more interactive and productive (Lin et al., 2017) as cited by Akram H, et al, 2022 as it offers various tools that are used in traditional as well as online teaching spaces and assist in building a proactive classroom environment (Jogezai et al., 2021). Technology-incorporated instructional practices not only enhance the quality of teaching (Akram et al., 2021) but also enable students to develop their skills, boost their motivation, and enhance their knowledge and information efficiently (Chen et al., 2018).

The teacher developers are mandated to cascade to their fellow teachers through Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions in the school under item 15.4 (21st Century Skills and ICT Integration in Instruction and Assessment) of DepEd Order No. 35, s. 2016 to enhance teaching and learning through interactive classroom instructions. Consistent with the mandate of the Department of Education Information and Communications Technology Service (ICTS) to oversee the proper implementation of the DepEd Computerization

Program (DCP) under DepEd Order No. 78, s. 2010 entitled Guidelines on the Implementation of the DepEd Computerization Program (DCP) (DepEd, 2019).

In light of these problems, the researcher was challenged to uncover the difficulties encountered by West II District teachers on ICT integration during the school year 2023-2024 in classroom teaching. Teachers at West II District encountered issues and disadvantages because they have varying levels of professional perspectives and ICT skills. This study also placed more emphasis on the difficulties teachers faced when incorporating technology into their lesson plans.

Hence, this research aimed to determine the teachers' professional perspectives and process of ICT integration in classroom teaching. The primary goal of the inquiry was to determine how technology was applied to the teaching and learning process. In addition, the proponent had a strong personal interest in the topic since she wanted to improve her students' classroom instruction. The researcher, who is also a teacher, proposed an intervention program that would improve teachers' ICT proficiency and classroom integration of computers.

Research Questions

The main thrust of this study was to determine teachers' professional perspectives on the use of computer technology and the process of ICT integration in classroom teaching. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. length of service;
 - 1.4. number of ICT pieces of training attended; and
 - 1.5. current teaching position?
2. What is the level of the respondents' professional perspective on the use of computer technology in the classroom?
3. What is the respondents' extent of using ICT process integration in terms of:
 - 3.1. instructional;
 - 3.2. informative;
 - 3.3. communicative;
 - 3.4. evaluative; and
 - 3.5. organizational?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' professional perspective and their ICT process of integration of the respondents?
5. Which of the respondents' demographic profiles best predicts their ICT process integration?
6. What action plan for classroom management can be proposed based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The method used in this study was the descriptive-correlational research design to obtain the data needed specifically using a survey questionnaire. The relationship between the respondent's demographic profile, professional perspectives, and process integration in terms of instructional, communicative, organizational, evaluative, and informative is the basis for the intervention program. A descriptive-correlational design is a research design that aims to determine the cause of the existing differences in the status of groups or individuals. The independent variable is believed to influence and cause an effect on the dependent variable. This method is the most appropriate since the purpose of the study is to determine if the teachers' professional perspectives on computer technology influence their ICT integration in classroom teaching.

Respondents

The matrix below shows the distribution of the teachers.

Table 1. *Respondents of the Study*

<i>Name of Schools</i>	<i>No. of Teachers</i>	<i>Random No. of Respondents</i>
Sgt. Miguel Canoy Memorial Central School	58	44
NAPOCOR Elementary Schol	36	27
Maria Cristina Falls Elementary School	22	17
Mimbalot Elementary School	21	16
Ditucalan Elementary School	22	17
Francesca Paradela Legaspi Memorial School	7	5
Total	166	126

The respondents of the study randomly selected 126 elementary public school teachers for the SY 2023-2024 as a secondary source of

data. These recipients had been selected because the researcher believed that respondents had their professional perspectives on how to integrate and use ICT in classroom teaching.

The researcher employed random sampling to generate the sample population of learners using the Raosoft calculator to determine the number of participants for kindergarten to grade 6 Teachers in West 2 District, Division of Iligan City as respondents of the study. A letter was given to the School Heads when the study was conducted.

Instrument

In this study, the Technology Implementation Questionnaire (TIQ) Version II tool was used. It was an adopted and modified instrument and developed by Wozney et al. (2006). It has an item Likert scale type of test that measures teacher professional perspectives related to computer technology questions answerable by a 4-point Likert Scale (1-Strongly Disagree, 2-Disagree, 3- Agree, 4-Strongly Agree). Fifteen (15) items for ICT integration questions were also answerable by a 4-point Likert Scale (1-Never, 2-Sometimes, 3-Often, 4-Always) and was divided into five subscales that measured respondents process of integration in terms of instructional (4 items), informative (4 items), communicative (4 items), evaluative (4 items), and organization (4 items). It was an instructional use for computers in the classroom instructions.

The data for respondents' demographic profiles was also included in the instrument. Teachers' profiles are composed of age, sex, length of service as a teacher, number of ICT pieces of training attended, and current teaching position. The instrument used in this study has a total number of forty (40) -items Likert scale type of test. This was administered to selected one hundred twenty-six teachers in West 2 District of Iligan City. The researcher used the TIQ: Version II instrument because it helps describe and understand differences between teachers in planning and implementing technology in classroom teaching.

Table 2. *Reliability Statistics Results*

Study Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items	Description
Professional Views	.906	30	Excellent
Process Integration			
Instructional	.863	5	Good
Informative	.864	5	Good
Communicative	.864	5	Good
Organizational	.856	5	Good
Over-all Reliability	.868	20	Good

Note: Cronbach's alpha above 0.7 is considered reliable
LEGENDS: (George & Mallery, 2023)

The questionnaire was pilot-tested at West 1 District. Hence, the validity of the instrument was not an issue. The instrument was used to measure and describe the respondents' level of professional perspectives and process of integration on the use of computer technology in the classroom.

Table 3. *Scoring Procedure and Interpretation of the Professional Views on Computer*

Rating	Scoring Scale	Qualitative Description	Qualitative Interpretation
4	3.49 – 4.32	Strongly Agree	Extremely High
3	2.67 – 3.50	Agree	High
2	1.83 – 2.66	Disagree	Low
1	1.00 – 1.82	Strongly Disagree	Extremely Low

Scoring System Table 3 shows the scoring procedure and interpretation of the professional perspectives on computer technology. The rating used is from 1 to 4 with a qualitative description of "strongly disagree" and "strongly agree" as the least and highest, respectively. The respondents indicated to what extent they strongly agreed (4) or strongly disagreed (1) with each item where there were no right or wrong answers. The adjacent qualitative interpretation from "never" to "always" was utilized to describe the perceived level of the respondents' professional perspectives on the use of computer technology in the classroom.

Table 4. *Table Scoring Procedure and Interpretation of the Process of Integration*

Rating	Scoring Scale	Qualitative Description	Qualitative Interpretation
4	3.49 – 4.32	Always	Extremely High
3	2.67 – 3.50	Often	High
2	1.83 – 2.66	Sometimes	Low
1	1.00 – 1.82	Never	Extremely Low

Table 4 shows the scoring procedure and interpretation of the process of computer technology integration. The rating used was from 1 to 4 with a qualitative description of "never" and "always" as the least and highest, respectively. The respondents indicated to what extent they always (4) or never (1) with each item where there were no right or wrong answers. The adjacent qualitative interpretation from "extremely low" to "extremely high" will be utilized to describe the perceived level of the respondents' process of integration on the use of computer technologies in the teaching and learning process.

Procedure

Initially, a permission letter to conduct the study was presented to the Schools Division Superintendent of Division of Iligan City. As soon as the letter of approval was permitted, the researcher approached the School Heads for courtesy regarding the conduct of the study. Then the questionnaires with the attached permission letter to the participants were distributed. Respondents are given enough time to answer the questionnaires at their convenient time. The questionnaires were given to the respondents last February 29, 2024.

Respondents were given instructions after receiving the different questionnaires. The questionnaires were distributed at the faculty's Learning Action Cell (LAC) meetings, giving respondents plenty of time to complete them while taking into account their comfort levels, preferred time slots, and general well-being. After the questionnaire was retrieved, the data gathered was tabulated, consolidated, analyzed, and interpreted through statistical treatment.

Data Analysis

The researcher employed a quantitative method of treating the data for analyses suited to the research problem mentioned in Chapter 1. These are basic and inferential statistical tools appropriate to the nature of the data sets gathered.

For problem 1, Frequency, and percentage distribution were used to describe the profile distribution of the respondents.

Problems 2 and 3, Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation. These basic descriptive statistical tools were used to describe and measure the central location and variation of the respondents' self-report assessment on their professional perspectives on the use of computer technology in the classroom and the extent of using ICT in terms of instructional, communicative, organizational, evaluative, and informative. Since these variables were measurable quantitatively through a Likert-scaled instrument with an appropriate scoring system.

Problem 4, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was utilized to determine the relationship between the respondents' professional perspective and their ICT process of integration.

Problem 5, Multiple Regression analysis with a simultaneous was utilized to test the predictors that significantly affected the professional perspective of the ICT process of respondents.

Results and Discussion

This section discusses the data that are shown in the tables. The data were analyzed, interpreted, and supported by related literature or studies. The presentation, interpretation, and analysis are supported tables and arranged in the same manner as the questions presented in the statement of the problem in Chapter 1.

Problem 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, length of service, number of ICT pieces of training attended, and current grade level taught?

Table 5. *Age of the Respondents*

<i>Age Bracket (yrs. Old)</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
26-30 years old	22	17.00
31-35 years old	14	11.00
36-40 years old	17	14.00
41-45 years old	20	16.00
46-50 years old	15	12.00
51 years old and above	38	30.00
Total	126	100.00

Table 5 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age. As depicted in the table, it showed that the highest number were coming from the age bracket between 51 and above years old which was 38 or 30% out of the 126 respondents. However, just 14 or 11% of respondents, or those from the age range of 31 to 35, were within this age range.

The results show that although older instructors have less ICT expertise, they are generally more open to utilizing new technology. The findings also show that most of the respondents aged between 26-30 years old prove that they are more knowledgeable when it comes to technology. The respondents were chosen at random from each school in the West 2 District, age was not a factor in the questionnaire distribution process by the school administrator.

However, it is also mentioned in other findings that despite experiencing similar learning difficulties, middle-aged women aged between 40 and 60 are more interested and excited to have opportunities to engage in future learning related to the practical knowledge, namely continuing technology education, compared to younger and male peers as cited by Jamil et al. (2023).

According to Laabidi (2016), The literature's conclusions about how age affects ICT integration in the classroom are contradictory. Kendel (1995), for example, concluded that the age component was statistically significant in that younger academics had more positive attitudes toward using ICT for educational goals. However, Chio (1992) found that teachers who are old tend to have more positive

attitudes toward the implementation of new technologies in teaching practices. Similarly, Spiegel & Shohamy (1989) as cited by Laabidi, (2016) examined the relationship between age and the use of ICT in classrooms. The findings of his study revealed that there was no significant correlation between teachers' age and their attitudes towards computer technologies.

Table 6. *Respondents' Sex*

Status	Frequency	Percentage
Male	14	11.00
Female	112	89.00
Total	126	100.00

Table 6 shows the respondent's profile in terms of civil status. It can be gleaned that the majority of the respondents were female, which is 112 out of 126 or 89%, while 11% or 14 of the respondents were male.

There is gender stereotyping and society's expectations about what should be the appropriate career paths for men and women as it can influence individuals' career choices. Teaching has often been associated with qualities such as patience, empathy, and communication skills—traits that align with stereotypical notions of femininity. While careers in fields such as science, technology, engineering, and mathematics are often perceived as more suitable for men, reinforcing gender disparities in teaching and other professions.

In addition to external aspects, gender problems in technology usage have been identified as a barrier in the last two decades. There are conflicting claims about the impact of gender on ICT pedagogy (Teo, 2008) as cited by Jamil, et al (2023). According to Jamil et al. (2023), Markauskaite (2006) found variations in the technical ICT ability that teachers, male and female, self-reported having. This succinct analysis shows that women can use technology and ought to have the same access to ICT-related information and resources as males.

Age and gender have been the subject of fewer studies on digital competency. Research indicates that younger instructors are more proficient in using digital technology than older teachers, while female teachers are less proficient than male teachers in this area. Peng et al. (2023), however, suggested that age and gender have less of an impact on digital competency.

Table 7. *Respondents' Length of Service*

Years	Frequency	Percentage
1-5 years	35	30.00
6-10 years	58	45.00
11-15 years	24	18.00
16 and above years	9	7.00
Total	126	100.00

Table 7 shows the distribution of the respondents according to their length of service. It revealed that the highest number are those who served for 6-10 years in the Department of Education whose frequency is 58 out of 126 or 45%. Followed by 35 respondents or 30% who served for about 1-5 years. The least number of respondents are those who have 16 and above years in the service which is 9 or only 7% out of the total 100%.

The findings from the study revealed that there was no significant relationship between the respondents' length of service since the respondents were randomly selected to answer the questionnaire.

According to Peng, (2023), several variables, such as instructors' age, gender, and degree of classroom experience, have an impact on how they see integrating ICT into teaching. It implied that attitudes toward the use of ICT in the classroom are correlated with the age group of the teachers. This applied to professors who were male or female. Meanwhile, novice instructors were more positive about the use of ICT in education than their more experienced counterparts. Some research, however, has discovered no variation in the ways that teachers utilize and perceive ICT according to gender, age, or experience level.

Table 8. *Respondents' Number of ICT Training Attended*

Number of Training	Frequency	Percentage
0 training	45	36.00
1-2 training	36	29.00
2-3 training	17	13.00
4 and above training	28	22.00
Total	126	100.00

Table 8 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of their number of ICT training. The majority have no training attended, which is 45 out of 126 respondents or 36%. The last teacher respondents are those who had attended 2-3 training courses, which was 17 or only 13 percent.

The Department of Education (DepEd) gives training to the teachers but not all teachers are allowed to attend ICT training. If there is, it is very rare to happen because sometimes only selected teachers can attend ICT training. Those who have been in the service longer than anticipated or who are older and perceive they are old enough to attend training will keep on offering training to newly hired or

inexperienced teachers.

Similar to the study of Wambiri and Nani (2020) in Kenya, teacher training revealed that there was a gap in the use of ICT. This was corroborated by a study conducted in 2019 by Muinde and Mbataru, which found that teachers' ICT training focused mostly on computer tools rather than ICT integration in the classroom. However, because they lacked the necessary technological skills, teachers found it difficult to integrate ICT into their lesson plans; however, this temporary period helped them become more proficient in digital media. According to Xu et al. (2021), several studies have also demonstrated the importance of ICT-integrated instructional approaches in meeting learners' educational needs by fostering a sense of thoughtfulness and maintaining student motivation.

As mentioned by Laabidi (2019) ICT integration into educational practices requires teacher training that should be built on both theoretical and practical competencies Hue & Ab Jalil, 2013 as cited by Jamil et al. 2023. Thus, it goes saying that teachers need to be trained and that training should focus on how to incorporate technology into pedagogical content and knowledge Harris et al., 2009 as noted by Jamil et al. 2023.

Table 9. Respondents' Assigned Grade Level

Grade Level	Frequency	Percentage
Kindergarten	20	16.00
Grade 1 and II	26	21.00
Grade III and IV	34	27.00
Grade V and VI	46	36.00
Total	126	100.00

From the presentation of table 9, it showed that 36% or 46 out of 126 respondents are handling Grades V and VI. The least number of respondents were the Kindergarten Teachers which is only 20 out of 126 or 16%. The study's findings demonstrated that there was no significant link between the respondents' assigned grade level and their questionnaire responses because the respondents were selected at random.

Various studies, regarding teachers' ICT implementation were revealed. The majority of high school English teachers and 20 elementary school teachers with more than ten years of experience teaching in their assigned grade level who participated in a survey on teachers' attitudes toward technology in language instruction were aware of the benefits of using ICT to teach every aspect of language that might improve students' achievement in language learning; however, because they lack ICT pedagogy and lack technical support from the schools, their teaching approach does not use ICT to its fullest extent, even though most teachers are digital immigrants as noted by (Harendita 2013; Hafifah, 2020; Jannah et al., 2020).

Problem 2: What is the level of the respondents' professional perspective on the use of computer technology in the classroom?

Table 10 presents the respondents' professional viewpoint on the usage of computers in the classroom. The results showed that on average teacher respondents have positive views as indicated in the average weighted mean of 3.422 which means they agree that using computer technology increases academic performance. Usage of instructional technologies makes it easier to prepare learning materials and has the highest weighted mean of 3.71. These tools offer access to a wide range of digital resources, like educational websites and online libraries. Teachers can design their materials, such as presentations and interactive activities. These technologies also allow for customization, so teachers can adjust materials to suit individual students' needs. By saving time and providing real-time updates, instructional technologies streamline the process of preparing materials, giving teachers more time to focus on teaching.

Table 10. Respondents' Level of Professional perspective on the Use of Computer Technology in the Classroom

Professional perspective Item statement	Weighted Mean	Remarks
PV1. Increases academic achievement (e.g., grades).	3.53	Strongly Agree
PV2. Use of ICT for instructional purposes is important rather than printed materials only	3.51	Strongly Agree
PV4. Promotes student collaboration	3.51	Strongly Agree
PV5. Use of ICT as an instructional tool can increase the interest of students in learning.	3.71	Strongly Agree
PV7. Is a valuable instructional tool	3.60	Strongly Agree
PV8. Computers can play a big role in instructional environments	3.61	Strongly Agree
PV9. Usage of instructional technologies makes it easier to prepare learning materials.	3.71	Strongly Agree
PV10. Makes teachers more productive as educators	3.65	Strongly Agree
PV11. Adequate teacher training in the use of technology for learning is relevant for classroom teaching.	3.61	Strongly Agree
PV12. Gives teachers the opportunity to be learning facilitators instead of information providers.	3.63	Strongly Agree
PV13. Using technology makes it easier to reach instructional resources	3.64	Strongly Agree
PV14. Technology makes things easier, particularly when it comes to helping students enhance their reading abilities through online reading resources.	3.56	Strongly Agree
PV15. Enhances my professional development	3.65	Strongly Agree
PV17. Is effective if teachers participate in the selection of computer technologies to be integrated.	3.51	Strongly Agree
PV19. Motivates students to get more involved in learning activities	3.57	Strongly Agree
Average	3.42	Strongly Agree

Note: 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50–2.49, Disagree; 2.50–3.49, Agree; 3.50–4.00, Strongly Agree.

The usage of ICT for instructional purposes is important rather than printed materials got the lowest weighted mean of 3.51. Using ICT for teaching is crucial because it offers many benefits that printed materials can't match. It gives users access to a wealth of online data and tools that can enhance instruction and increase student interest. With ICT, teachers can use multimedia elements like videos, interactive simulations, and online quizzes to explain concepts more visually and interactively. This helps students better understand and remember what they're learning. Personalized learning experiences are another benefit of ICT, enabling students to study subjects at their own pace and revisit them as needed.

Most respondents to the study thought that computers were important for learning and teaching, and they knew how to use them as a means of instruction.

It stressed how successful the teaching and learning process is when ICT is used in the classroom, which encourages quality learning. This result concurred with Permata and Purnawarman (2024) said that teachers use learning media to help them understand concepts and ideas more clearly and motivate students to be more active and think critically.

Table 11. Respondents' Level of Professional perspective on the Use of Computer Technology in the Classroom

Professional perspective Item statement	Weighted Mean	Remarks
PV3. Is effective because I believe I can implement it successfully.	3.46	Agree
PV6. Promotes the development of communication skills (e.g., writing and presentation skills).	3.46	Agree
PV16. Assess the pressure on me as a teacher.	3.46	Agree
PV18. Helps accommodate students' learning styles	3.45	Agree
PV20. Could reduce the number of teachers employed in the future	2.73	Agree
PV21. Limits my choices of instructional materials	2.75	Agree
PV22. Requires software skills training that is too time-consuming.	2.90	Agree
PV23. Promotes the development of students' interpersonal skills. (e.g., ability to relate or work with others).	3.30	Agree
PV24. This will increase the amount of stress and anxiety students experience.	2.74	Agree
PV25. Is effective only when extensive computer resources are available	3.11	Agree
PV26. Is difficult because some students know more about computers than many teachers do.	2.88	Agree
PV27. Is only successful if computer technology is part of the student's home environment	3.11	Agree
PV28. Requires extra time to plan learning activities.	2.97	Agree
PV29. Improves student learning of critical concepts and ideas.	3.30	Agree
PV30. Becomes more important to me if the student does not have access to a computer at home.	2.72	Agree
Average	3.42	Agree

Note: 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50–2.49, Disagree; 2.50–3.49, Agree; 3.50–4.00, Strongly Agree.

ICT promotes the development of communication skills and has the highest weighted mean of 3.46 also the statement ICT is effective because I can implement it successfully. When students collaborate on projects using digital platforms, they learn how to express their ideas online. Online discussions or video calls allow students to practice effective communication by expressing their thoughts, listening to others, and responding appropriately. ICT also encourages students to communicate with a wider audience beyond the classroom.

As mentioned by Peng et al. (2023), attitudes mean a person's psychological evaluations of an object, individual, or event. Teachers need to have a positive attitude to use ICT effectively and creatively, as numerous studies have shown that attitudes have a beneficial impact on ICT integration. Numerous research projects have started to look at the connections between teachers' attitudes and their use of digital technologies and digital competency. It was found that the opinions of instructors significantly influenced their usage of digital resources and digital proficiency.

It also negates that some studies suggest that using ICT is not necessarily beneficial for learning. Actually, rather than utilizing ICT for learning-enhancing activities, kids can use it for social media activities or to watch funny videos. From a theoretical perspective, the displacement hypothesis expects such a negative association because of the time that should be spent on activities that improve academic skills according to Sanfo (2023).

As noted by Kilag et al. (2023), classroom instruction is being improved by the use of technology. It increases the number of available courses, learning opportunities, and learning resources; facilitates studying around the clock, seven days a week; fosters the development of 21st-century skills; increases student motivation and engagement; and expedites learning. Technology can also revolutionize education by bringing about a new linked teaching paradigm.

Problem 3: What is the respondents' extent of using ICT process integration in terms of instructional, informative, communicative, evaluative, and organizational?

Table 12 shows the respondents' ICT process integration in terms of instruction. Accordingly, the indicator "Use MELC-based local videos (YouTube) in (YouTube) in your lessons." displayed the highest weighted mean of 3.42 indicating that respondents emphasized the importance of incorporating digital resources, specifically MELC-based local videos available on YouTube, as part of the instructional strategies employed by teachers.

As mentioned by Hutton, 2020 and cited by Ong et al. (2023) Zoom and Google Meet are video conferencing tools used for the delivery

of synchronous online lessons and giving of instructional activities.

Table 12. Respondents' Instructional ICT Process Instructional Integration

<i>Instructional ICT Process Integration</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
III1. Use MELC-based local videos (YouTube) in your lessons.	3.42	Often
III2. Use tutorials for self-training using video lessons. (Online resources)	3.22	Often
III3. Have students use downloadable printed worksheets for remediation/activities in class.	3.25	Often
III4. Use Google Classroom/Google Meet for instructional questions/activities.	2.47	Sometimes
Average	3.09	Often

Note: 1.00–1.49, Never; 1.50–2.49, Sometimes; 2.50–3.49, Often; 3.50–4.00, Always

Scholarly works have shown the benefits of virtual education in terms of enabling learners to participate in the cognitive and social aspects of knowledge creation (Quek, 2007). The interactions and cooperation made possible by technologies like Google Workspace can help achieve this (Choy & Quek, 2016). Additionally, teachers found it difficult to diversify instruction and choose the right digital tools due to the abundance of tools available through the Internet (Sabarinath & Quek, 2020). Teachers now have to reconsider their lesson plans, tool choices, and classroom relationships as a result of this experience. Education systems across the globe have emphasized their academic agendas to adapt strategies or policies around information and communication technology (ICT) integration (European Commission, 2019), as cited by Timotheou, S., and have increased their investment in ICT integration by Fernández-Gutiérrez et al., 2020; Lawrence and Tar, 2023.

Further, the respondents rated the lowest the indicator “Use Google Classroom/Google Meet for instructional questions/activities.” with a weighted mean of 2.47. This implied that only a few teachers use Google Classroom/Google Meet to give instructional questions/activities to their learners.

Table 13. Respondents' Informative ICT Process Integration

<i>Informative ICT Process Integration</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
IPI1. Search the Internet for information for a lesson	3.59	Always
IPI2. Access YouTube as reference material	3.57	Always
IPI3. Use of online platforms for learners' activities. (Quizzes.com, Read Along App, YouTube)	3.01	Often
IPI4. Share awareness from a post on Facebook in the parents' group chat.	2.55	Often
Average	3.18	Often

Note: 1.00–1.49, Never; 1.50–2.49, Sometimes; 2.50–3.49, Often; 3.50–4.00, Always

Table 13 presents the level of respondents' ICT process integration in terms of informative practices. Accordingly, the indicator “Search the Internet for information for a lesson” has the highest weighted mean of 3.59. The results revealed that the respondents always search the internet for information for a lesson. This further suggests that responders are capable of using the internet to browse and conduct searches for additional material to support their class topic. The Internet is essential for education, according to a study by Sharna (2019). Teachers use search engines like Google to look up solutions to problems, questions, and other issues they may have.

On the other hand, the indicator “Share awareness from a post on Facebook in the parents' group chat.” has the lowest mean of 2.55. This outcome showed that not all parents have access using Messenger.

As cited by Masnawati and Kurniawan, (2023) the integration of technology in education enables students to engage with interactive learning materials, access a wealth of educational resources, and collaborate with peers in real time. The seamless interaction facilitated by social networks promotes active participation, knowledge sharing, and critical thinking, ultimately leading to enhanced academic outcomes.

Furthermore, the utilization of information technology offers personalized learning experiences tailored to individual student needs and learning styles. Adaptive learning platforms and intelligent educational tools leverage data-driven insights to provide targeted instruction and support, addressing students' unique strengths and areas of improvement. This personalized approach enhances engagement, motivation, and knowledge retention, ultimately contributing to more favorable learning outcomes. Educational institutions and policymakers should recognize the transformative potential of information technology and invest in robust infrastructure, professional development, and curriculum integration to harness its full benefits. By embracing technology-enabled learning environments and fostering a culture of innovation, educators can create dynamic and inclusive educational experiences that empower students to thrive in the digital age.

Table 14. Respondents' ICT Communicative Process Integration

<i>Communicative ICT Process Integration</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
CIPI1. Use Group Chat/Messenger to communicate with other teachers.	3.73	Always
CIPI2. Use Google Drive to share files with other teachers.	3.42	Often
CIPI3. Inform parents through messenger/text.	3.50	Always
CIPI4. Use email to communicate with other teachers.	2.55	Often
Average	3.47	Often

Note: 1.00–1.49, Never; 1.50–2.49, Sometimes; 2.50–3.49, Often; 3.50–4.00, Always

Table 14 presents the respondents' level of communicative ICT process integration. Based on the results, among the enumerated indicators of describing the respondent's extent of using ICT in communication, the indicator "Use Group Chat/Messenger to communicate with other teachers." obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.73. This implies that the majority of the respondents using group chat is easy to use group chat platforms offer a convenient and efficient way for teachers to communicate with each other. The majority of these studies have concentrated on the typical applications of chatbots and/or messaging apps to provide anytime, anywhere tailored instruction in classrooms Panah and Babar (2020), as referenced by Merelo, (2023) along with others.

However, indicator number four "Use email to communicate with other teachers." got the lowest mean of 2.55. While newer communication technologies such as instant messaging apps and social media platforms have gained popularity, email continues to be a staple in professional communication.

Table 15. Respondents' ICT Evaluative Process Integration

<i>Evaluative ICT Process Integration</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
EIPI1. Test or assess student learning with the use of technology.	3.20	Often
EIPI2. Use Google link, and Microsoft Excel to answer questions/information.	3.02	Often
EIPI3. Use of PowerPoint presentations as review materials for learners	3.35	Often
EIPI4. Assess learners using the classmarker.com online platform.	2.31	Sometimes
Average	2.97	Often

Note: 1.00–1.49, Never; 1.50–2.49, Sometimes; 2.50–3.49, Often; 3.50–4.00, Always

Table 15 presents the level of evaluative ICT process integration of the respondents. Findings revealed that teachers often use PowerPoint presentations as review materials for learners which got a 3.20 weighted mean. This suggests that respondents have assessed their students using technology.

According to Deepa's (2020) study, instructors have grown accustomed to adopting c-assessment in the classroom because of its practicality, adaptability, and accessibility. Perhaps some of the respondents have used Google Forms for electronic assessment, which enables teachers to quickly and accurately check and record students' test results. However, indicator number four "Assess learners using classmarker.com online platform." got the lowest weighted mean of 2.31. This implies that not all learners have access to classmarker.com because some students don't have gadgets or internet connections to access it.

As cited by Awidi and Paynter, Digital Technologies (DTs) in 2024 are electronic tools, resources, and systems such as social media, online resources, mobile devices, and multimedia that generate, receive, process, store, and communicate information (Camilleri & Camilleri, 2017, 2021). Digitally literate students can access educational materials via a range of online platforms, including video games, tablets, smartphones, social media platforms, YouTube, and mobile devices (Camilleri & Camilleri, 2021; Hatzipanagos & John, 2017; Johannesen et al., 2019). With the help of these online tools, driven and tech-savvy students may make sense of and reinforce what they have learned in lectures (Bueno-Ravel & Gueudet, 2009; Jacob-sen, 2019; Pillutla et al., 2020).

Thus, it may be argued that lecturers are now able to deliver teaching and learning more flexibly and engagingly for students. Some experts, nevertheless, are less certain that digital technology will improve schooling. These authors concluded that institutions can better both the overall student experience and academic outcomes through the systematic reform of curricula employing technology-enhanced learning. Researcher support for that funding has been provided by Camilleri and Camilleri (2017), Stec et al. (2020), and Voogt and Knezek (2018).

Table 16. Respondents' Organizational ICT Process Integration

<i>Organizational ICT Process Integration</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
OIPI1. Keep track of student grades or marks with the use of technology. (Microsoft Excel)	3.55	Always
OIPI2. Prepare handouts, tests/quizzes, and homework assignments for students with the use of technology	3.50	Always
OIPI3. Create Daily Lesson Logs/Lesson Plans with the use of technology. (Downloadable files online)	3.54	Always
OIPI4. Use digital portfolios for learners' activities. (Canva/Photoshop, Games Online, etc.)	3.23	Often
Average	3.45	Often

Note: 1.00–1.49, Never; 1.50–2.49, Sometimes; 2.50–3.49, Often; 3.50–4.00, Always

Table 16 presents the level of organizational ICT process integration of the respondents. Findings revealed that teachers often keep track of student grades or marks with the use of technology. Using Microsoft Excel to keep track of student grades offers a user-friendly, customizable, and efficient solution for teachers to manage grading tasks and monitor student progress effectively. However, indicator number four "Use digital portfolios for learners' activities. (Canva/Photoshop, Games Online, etc.)" got the lowest weighted mean of 3.23. This could be viewed as evidence that the use of ICT in education has had a favorable impact on educational quality. Teachers now use computers for a variety of tasks in the classrooms, such as planning, integrating technology into lessons, and evaluating students.

Wijayasundara (2015), as cited by Shaheen and Shah, 2019 who emphasized that education becomes effective and beneficial when it is accumulated and improved with computer technology, backed this up. It makes sense that technology has become a significant component of the educational system.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' professional perspective and their ICT process of integration of the respondents?

Table 17. *Regression Analysis Results between the Respondents' Professional Perspective and their ICT Process Integration.*

ICT Process Integration	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Instructional	2.930	0.004	Significant
Informative	0.996	0.321	Not Significant
Communicative	3.267	0.001	Significant
Evaluative	2.253	0.026	Significant
Organizational	2.835	0.005	Significant

Note: ANOVA for Regression: $F=8.585$, Significant at 0.01 level, $R^2=.265$

The results from regression analysis for the significant relationship between the respondents' perspective and their ICT process integration in terms of instructional, informative, communicative, evaluative, and organizational shows that there is a positive relationship among the variables mentioned except the informative ICT process integration which has a p-value of 0.321 greater than 0.05 level of significance.

This implies that the professional perspective of the teachers has a positive influence on their ICT process integration in the classroom. The professional perspective of teachers plays a significant role in shaping their attitudes, beliefs, and practices related to ICT integration in the classroom. Peng et al. (2023) noted that several factors, such as teachers' age, gender, and degree of classroom experience, had an impact on their opinions about integrating ICT into courses. It implied that attitudes toward the use of ICT in the classroom are correlated with the age group of the teachers. This applied to professors who were male or female. Meanwhile, novice instructors were more positive about the use of ICT in education than their more experienced counterparts. Some research, however, has discovered no variation in the ways that teachers utilize and perceive ICT according to gender, age, or experience level.

Hence, the respondents' extent of using ICT in instruction is good and acceptable in terms of the instructional, informative, communicative, evaluative, and organizational that are common components of the teaching and learning process (Pedagoo, 2020). This further implies that respondents' average computer skills affect their level of process of integration in the classroom. To be competent in utilizing technology for instructional purposes and other school-related tasks, teachers should commit to increasing existing computer knowledge and skills.

According to Sharna (2019) and Gomez (2015), studies that technology plays a vital role in education. Teachers use computers and the internet to search for information for their class lessons. The internet has become the source of updated and latest information.

Problem 5: Which of the respondents' demographic profiles best predicts their ICT process integration?

Table 18. *Demographic Profile that best predicts Respondents' ICT Process Integration*

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Remarks
	B	Beta	t	p-value	
(Constant)	3.516			0.000	
Age	-0.014	-0.274	-1.648	0.102	Not Significant
Sex	-0.093	-0.055	-0.592	0.555	Not Significant
Length of Service	0.040	0.125	0.745	0.458	Not Significant
Number of ICT Training	0.023	0.051	0.560	0.577	Not Significant
Grade Level assigned	0.052	0.107	1.108	0.270	Not Significant
	R = 0.334 F = 1.199 Sig. = 0.05				

Table 18 presented the results of regression analysis between the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, length of service, number of ICT training, and grade level assigned as predictors of their ICT process integration. Results showed that all of the mentioned demographic profiles are not predictors of their ICT process integration as indicated in their p-values greater than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the result shows that participants enjoy the use of computers but lack competence in using them. According to the results of the research conducted by Subekti and Kurniawati (2022), even though the teachers use excessively basic instructional technology, they conveyed their excitement for using ICT to help them become more creative, competent, and interactive in their teaching, which enhanced their relationship with their students and changed the way they teach.

Similarly, Coleman et al., (2019) stressed that successful implementation of technology into classroom instructions gives large adjustment for educators as well as learners. The whole class must participate in the more interactive nature of teaching. The main purpose of ICT integration in school settings is to promote government policies and goals for the advancement of ICT in education. However, it can be challenging to integrate ICT in a classroom setting since problems can arise, especially during the initial phases of deployment, which could lead to failure. As stated by Kendel (1995), referenced by Laabidi, H. (2019) The research has produced

contradictory results about the impact of age on ICT integration in the classroom. He concluded, for example, that the age component was of statistical importance in that younger academics had more positive attitudes toward using ICT for educational goals. Nevertheless, Chio (1992), referenced by Laabidi, H. (2019) discovered that older educators typically exhibit more favorable sentiments on the incorporation of new technologies into the classroom.

Various studies, regarding teachers' ICT implementation were revealed. In a survey on teachers' attitudes toward technology in language instruction, the majority of high school English teachers and 20 elementary schools teachers with above ten years of teaching experience who participated were aware of the advantages of utilizing ICT to teach every aspect of language that might improve students' achievement in language learning, but their teaching approach does not use ICT to its fullest ability due to their lack of ICT pedagogy and lack of technical support from schools, even though the vast majority of educators are digital natives (Harendita 2013; Hafifah, 2020; Jannah et al., 2020).

Problem 6: What action plan for classroom management can be proposed based on the results of the study?

Integrating computer technology in education helps the teaching and learning process in various ways. It makes learning more relatable, innovative deeper, exciting, and more personalized to each student. A teacher should therefore have adequate ICT knowledge and abilities to use these resources for their own professional and personal development in addition to the process of instruction and learning. The goal of this program is to give teachers the information and tools they need to employ various technologies in the classroom.

Conclusions

Based on the findings drawn, the study concludes:

The professional perspective of the respondents on the use of computer technology in the classroom. There is no significant difference in the factors affecting the respondent's professional perspective on the use of computer technology in the classroom. The results showed that on average teacher respondents have positive views as indicated in the average weighted mean of 3.422 which means they agree that using computer technology increases academic performance.

The results from regression analysis for the significant relationship between the respondents' professional view and their ICT process integration in terms of instructional, informative, communicative, evaluative, and organizational shows that there is a positive relationship among the variables mentioned except the informative ICT process integration which has a p-value of 0.321 greater than 0.05 level of significance.

This implies that the professional perspective of the teachers has a positive influence on their ICT process integration in the classroom. The professional perspective of teachers plays a significant role in shaping their attitudes, beliefs, and practices related to ICT integration in the classroom.

Results of regression analysis between the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, length of service, number of ICT training, and grade level assigned as predictors of their ICT process integration. Results showed that all of the mentioned demographic profiles are not predictors of their ICT process integration as indicated in their p-values greater than 0.05 level of significance.

The following recommendations are given below:

To the School Heads. They scrutinized the results of the teachers' Self-Assessment Tool (SAT) and the Individual Performance and Commitment Review Form (ICRF) to determine the teachers' weaknesses in terms of ICT utilization. Through this, they should design relevant and timely Learning Action Cells (LACs) or In-Service teacher training aimed at improving teachers' ICT skills and computer technology integration in the classroom. Moreover, they should recall the availability of computers/ hardware and internet availability in their school. This will motivate teachers to prepare digitally based teaching materials and allow them to design collaborative activities, practicum, and research-based activities for their students.

To the Teachers. They perform self-reflection on the extent of using computer technology in the classroom, perform self-evaluation on their ICT skills, and attend training, seminars, or symposia on how to integrate and maximize ICT skills in their instruction. Upskilling and reskilling of ICT skills are crucial in developing self-confidence in computer integration in classroom instructions.

To the Future Researchers. They might find the result of this study relevant to be used in their future research.

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